

HUMAN RIGHTS VIOLATIONS AND POLICE CONDUCT IN NIGERIA: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF THE NIGERIAN POLICE IN OGUN STATE

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Abstract

This study investigates human rights violations and police conduct in Nigeria, with specific attention to the Nigerian Police in selected local government areas of Ogun State. The study is situated within the broader national concern over rising incidents of police brutality, unlawful arrests, extrajudicial killings, and related abuses that continue to undermine public trust in law enforcement. The population of the study comprised residents of Abeokuta South, Ijebu North, and Ado-Odo/Ota Local Government Areas, totaling 1,200 respondents. A multistage sampling technique was used to select participants, and data were collected through a structured questionnaire designed to capture experiences and perceptions of police activities. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including frequency counts and simple percentage. Findings reveal widespread human rights violations, notably police brutality, unlawful detention, bribery, extortion, extrajudicial killings, and suppression of peaceful protests. The study further identifies systemic issues such as corruption, political interference, weak enforcement of legal frameworks, poor working conditions, and entrenched impunity as major drivers of police misconduct. The analysis shows that these violations have significantly eroded public trust in the Nigerian Police. The study concludes that persistent human rights abuses are sustained by weak accountability mechanisms and ineffective implementation of reforms. It recommends strengthening legal and institutional frameworks, enforcing disciplinary measures, enhancing human rights training for officers, and establishing independent oversight bodies. Additionally, citizens should be encouraged to report abuses and participate in civic advocacy aimed at promoting transparent and accountable policing practices.

Keywords: Human rights violations, police conduct, Nigerian Police, accountability, Ogun State

Introduction

Despite over a decade of democratic governance and Nigeria's endorsement of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, human rights abuses remain pervasive across the country. Nigeria frequently exhibits authoritarian tendencies in both leadership and security operations, resulting in widespread violations. Otodo, Otigbuo, Bako, and Aaron (2024) observed that such violations have become ingrained in a culture of impunity, including extra-judicial killings, unlawful detention, and the destruction of property by security forces. Similarly, other forms of abuse, such as the harassment and extortion of motorists, political assassinations, the undemocratic imposition of candidates, and the intimidation of political opponents, have been rampant among security agents in Nigeria (Akhaine & Chizea, 2011; Mela, Garba, & Osanubi, 2022).

Law enforcement agents operate with impunity in the apprehension, detention, and even extrajudicial killing of criminal suspects (Imegi, 2023). Authorities generally fail to hold the police accountable for excessive or lethal force or for deaths occurring in custody (Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999). While research on security agencies and human rights violations in Nigeria is both timely and crucial, it remains underrepresented in Nigerian academic literature. Although studies on human rights violations by security agencies were conducted in the past, rapid global changes, including technological advancements, shifts in governance, environmental factors, and the impact of COVID-19 amongst others have rendered many of their findings obsolete. Given the emergence of new administrations and evolving institutional practices, further research is essential to determine the extent of these violations, the challenges involved, and potential remedial measures (Mela et al; 2022).

Fundamentally, human rights according to Donnelly (2013), Bantekas and Oette (2016) refer to the basic rights and freedoms inherent to every individual, irrespective of background, lifestyle choices, or religious beliefs. These rights, rooted in universally shared values such as respect, dignity, equity, fairness, equality, and independence, are legally protected and defined. International human rights frameworks stipulate that no individual should be subjected to extreme abuse under any circumstances. However, in Nigeria, including the South-West region, citizens continue to encounter various forms of human rights violations arising from the conduct of law enforcement agencies. In Ogun State, residents frequently report incidents such as police brutality, unlawful arrests, extortion, intimidation, harassment at checkpoints, and suppression of peaceful civic activities. These violations undermine public safety, erode trust in law enforcement, and negatively affect the social and psychological wellbeing of individuals and communities. The situation underscores the need for effective measures to ensure accountability, strengthen police oversight, and promote the protection of human rights within the State.

Human rights, as a universal concept, define the relationship between individuals and power structures, particularly the state (Inter-Parliamentary Union & UN, 2016). Historically, struggles for human rights have shaped societies, from the French and American revolutions to modern democratic movements (Philip, 2018). These rights encompass civil, political, economic, and social entitlements (Obiora & Onwughalu, 2018). In Nigeria, Chapter Four of the 1999 Constitution guarantees fundamental rights but allows for their restriction under certain conditions (Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999). A nation's international image is shaped by its domestic policies and the conduct of its citizens abroad (Zimako, 2009). Positive global perception enhances a country's influence, while human rights violations can damage its reputation (Chidozie et al., 2014). Nigeria's international standing has been impacted by reports of rights abuses, necessitating strategic efforts to improve its image (Adeniyi, 2012).

Empirical Review

Otodo, Otigbuo, Bako, and Aaron (2024) evaluated the Nigerian government's commitment to addressing human rights abuses, particularly police brutality, in the aftermath of the EndSARS protests. The study examined the impact of post-EndSARS government policies, the relationship between law enforcement reforms and institutional changes, and the extent to which government actions influenced public perceptions of responsiveness. Using a survey method, data were collected from 381 respondents in Owerri, Imo State, and analysed through descriptive statistics, including means and standard deviation. Findings revealed mixed perceptions regarding the effectiveness of government interventions. While some progress was acknowledged, skepticism

remained about the overall impact of reforms. Law enforcement changes failed to enhance transparency and accountability or align with international standards, and government commitments were met with doubt. Additionally, there was no clear consensus on whether government actions had improved citizen perceptions of responsiveness. The study recommended stronger policy implementation and monitoring, prioritisation of institutional reforms within law enforcement agencies, greater commitment to substantive changes, and enhanced citizen engagement. Ultimately, it highlighted the complexities of tackling police brutality and human rights violations in Nigeria post-EndSARS, emphasising the need for sustained government action and public participation in reform efforts.

Obi and Uzodinma (2024) examined the impact of human rights violations on Nigeria's international image between 2015 and 2023. The study adopted an ex post facto research design, relying on documentary sources for data collection. The empirical data gathered were subjected to content analysis, revealing that human rights violations by security agencies reached alarming levels during this period. Furthermore, the study found that these widespread civil and human rights abuses severely damaged Nigeria's international reputation, as the Muhammadu Buhari administration struggled to address these irregularities effectively. Based on these findings, the study recommends the enactment of enabling legislation, increased advocacy, and comprehensive police reforms as essential measures to curb human rights violations and improve Nigeria's global standing.

Imegi (2023) investigated human rights violations in Nigeria, with a particular focus on police brutality. The study employed the doctrinal research method to examine various forms of police misconduct that undermine human rights and contribute to insecurity. The findings revealed that police brutality manifests in multiple ways, including torture to extract confessions, illegal detention, bribery and corruption, intimidation, molestation, rape, extrajudicial killings, and disregard for court orders. In response to these violations, the study recommended making human rights education compulsory at all levels of education, especially in Police Colleges and academies. Additionally, it emphasised the need for police authorities to prioritise human rights training during the recruitment and training of constables, as they are often the primary perpetrators of such abuses.

Ndukwe, Nwokwu, and Edeh (2023) investigated the role of security agencies in safeguarding fundamental human rights in Nigeria, given their significance in ensuring peace, security, and justice. The study was grounded in the social contract theory, originally formulated by Thomas Hobbes (1651). Employing a qualitative approach, the research critically analysed existing literature, drawing data from secondary sources such as scholarly articles, official reports, and other pertinent publications. The findings revealed that institutions tasked with protecting citizens often neglect their responsibilities, thereby exposing individuals to various forms of premeditated violence across the country. Furthermore, security agencies have been implicated in persistently denying citizens their rights. The study underscored the grave implications of such failures, suggesting that if the authorities continue to disregard their duty to safeguard lives and property, society risks descending into a chaotic and lawless state akin to Hobbes' depiction of the state of nature. In response to these findings, the study recommended that the government exhibit genuine political will in upholding and protecting citizens' rights, that human rights education be integrated into the national curriculum from primary to tertiary levels, and that

security agencies remain committed to their responsibilities by ensuring the safety and security of individuals and their property.

Theoretical Review

Gabriel Almond, an American political scientist, introduced the structural-functional systems theory in the mid-20th century. This theoretical framework analyses political systems by examining the structures (institutions and organisations) and their functions (roles and activities) within a society. Almond's approach emphasises understanding how various components of a political system interact to maintain stability and achieve collective goals. In the context of the study "Security Agencies and Human Right Violations in Nigeria" by Bello and Mela (2022), Almond's systems theory serves as the analytical lens. The theory posits that society operates as an interconnected system where each unit performs specific functions essential for the system's survival. Applying this to Nigeria, security agencies are integral structures expected to uphold law and order, thereby contributing to societal stability.

Methodology

The study adopted a survey research design to investigate the role of security agencies in human rights violations across selected local government areas in Ogun State. This design was chosen because it allowed for the systematic collection of data from a large population, enabling a comprehensive analysis of residents' experiences and perceptions regarding security operations and human rights abuses. The study focused on all residents across the existing local governments in Ogun State, as they represented diverse socio-political and economic backgrounds. To ensure fair representation, a multistage sampling technique was employed. Ogun State was first stratified into its three senatorial districts: Ogun Central, Ogun East, and Ogun West. From each district, a local government area was purposively selected based on its demographic importance, security challenges, and interactions between security operatives and civilians. Abeokuta South was chosen to represent Ogun Central due to its status as the state capital, where numerous protests and security operations had taken place. Ijebu North was selected for Ogun East, given its high population and history of security-related disputes, while Ado-Odo/Ota was chosen for Ogun West due to its industrial significance and frequent clashes between security forces and residents.

According to Ogun State Government (2024), the selected local governments in 2025 were 425,502 for Abeokuta South, 476,884 for Ijebu North, and 896,311 for Ado-Odo/Ota. The sample size for the study was determined using Taro Yamane's formula, which accounts for the total population and a 5% margin of error. Based on these calculations, 399 respondents were selected from Abeokuta South, 400 from Ijebu North, and 400 from Ado-Odo/Ota, bringing the total sample size to approximately 1,200. This sample was considered sufficient to ensure statistical reliability and the generalizability of findings. Data collection was carried out using a structured questionnaire, which was designed to capture respondents' personal experiences, perceptions, and interactions with security agencies. The questionnaire included both closed and open-ended questions to allow for a mix of quantitative and qualitative insights. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, which provided a clear summary of trends and patterns in human rights violations as perceived by residents. The methodological approach ensured that the study generated empirical evidence on the nature, extent, and implications of security-related human rights abuses in Ogun State.

Objectives of the Study

- i. Examine the prevalence and nature of human rights violations committed by the Nigerian Police in Ogun State.
- ii. Identify the factors contributing to human rights violations by the Nigerian Police.
- iii. Assess the impact of human rights violations on public trust in law enforcement and community-police relations in Ogun State.
- iv. Evaluate the effectiveness of legal and institutional mechanisms designed to prevent and address human rights abuses within the Nigerian Police.

Findings and Interpretation

Table 1: Prevalence and nature of human rights violations committed by the Nigerian Police

Statement	Strongly Disagree n(%)	Disagree n(%)	Neutral n(%)	Agree n(%)	Strongly Agree n(%)	Mean Score	Interpretation
Cases of police brutality are common.	56 (5.0%)	89 (8.0%)	145 (13.0%)	340 (30.5%)	485 (43.5%)	3.99	High Prevalence
Unlawful detention is frequent.	45 (4.0%)	78 (7.0%)	134 (12.0%)	378 (34.0%)	480 (43.0%)	4.05	High Prevalence
Extrajudicial killings are widespread.	67 (6.0%)	112 (10.0%)	190 (17.0%)	312 (28.0%)	434 (39.0%)	3.84	Moderate to High
Police officers engage in bribery/extortion.	34 (3.0%)	67 (6.0%)	111 (10.0%)	390 (35.0%)	513 (46.0%)	4.15	High Prevalence
Victims rarely receive justice.	56 (5.0%)	101 (9.0%)	168 (15.0%)	345 (31.0%)	445 (40.0%)	3.92	High Prevalence
Police violate rights to peaceful assembly.	45 (4.0%)	78 (7.0%)	134 (12.0%)	389 (35.0%)	469 (42.0%)	4.04	High Prevalence
Citizens distrust the police due to violations.	34 (3.0%)	89 (8.0%)	134 (12.0%)	367 (33.0%)	491 (44.0%)	4.07	High Prevalence

Table 1 presents the prevalence and nature of human rights violations committed by the Nigerian Police in Ogun State. The findings indicate a high prevalence of various forms of police misconduct, as reflected in the mean scores across the seven statements. Notably, bribery and extortion recorded the highest mean score (4.15), with 81% (Agree + Strongly Agree) of respondents acknowledging its frequency, reinforcing concerns about corruption within the police force. Similarly, unlawful detention (4.05) and citizens' distrust in the police due to

violations (4.07) highlight deep-seated systemic issues affecting public confidence. Cases of police brutality (3.99) and violations of the right to peaceful assembly (4.04) also received high agreement levels, further illustrating the widespread nature of police abuse. While extrajudicial killings (3.84) had a slightly lower mean score, the 67% agreement rate still suggests a significant occurrence of such incidents. Additionally, the perception that victims rarely receive justice (3.92) underscores the lack of accountability in addressing human rights violations.

Table 2: Factors Contributing to Human Rights Violations by the Nigerian Police in Ogun State

Statement	Strongly Disagree n(%)	Disagree n(%)	Neutral n(%)	Agree n(%)	Strongly Agree n(%)	Mean Score	Interpretation
Lack of proper police training leads to human rights abuses.	45 (4.0%)	89 (8.0%)	156 (14.0%)	378 (34.0%)	447 (40.0%)	3.98	High Contribution
Weak enforcement of laws against police misconduct encourages violations.	34 (3.0%)	67 (6.0%)	145 (13.0%)	401 (36.0%)	468 (42.0%)	4.08	High Contribution
Corruption within the police force fosters rights violations.	23 (2.0%)	56 (5.0%)	112 (10.0%)	390 (35.0%)	534 (48.0%)	4.22	High Contribution
Political interference prevents accountability for police misconduct.	56 (5.0%)	78 (7.0%)	134 (12.0%)	389 (35.0%)	458 (41.0%)	4.00	High Contribution
Inadequate police funding results in reliance on illegal practices.	45 (4.0%)	101 (9.0%)	167 (15.0%)	378 (34.0%)	424 (38.0%)	3.93	High Contribution
A culture of impunity within the police encourages violations.	34 (3.0%)	78 (7.0%)	145 (13.0%)	389 (35.0%)	469 (42.0%)	4.06	High Contribution

Poor working conditions make officers resort to illegal activities.	67 (6.0%)	112 (10.0%)	178 (16.0%)	356 (32.0%)	402 (36.0%)	3.82	Moderate to High Contribution
Public fear and lack of complaints enable continued abuses.	45 (4.0%)	89 (8.0%)	156 (14.0%)	367 (33.0%)	458 (41.0%)	3.99	High Contribution

Table 2 illustrates the factors contributing to human rights violations by the Nigerian Police in Ogun State. The results indicate that corruption within the police force (Mean = 4.22) is perceived as the most significant factor, with 83% of respondents (Agree + Strongly Agree) acknowledging its role in fostering rights abuses. Weak enforcement of laws (4.08) and a culture of impunity (4.06) also scored high, suggesting that the lack of accountability mechanisms allows violations to persist unchecked. Similarly, political interference (4.00) and public fear of reporting abuses (3.99) were identified as major obstacles to justice. The role of poor working conditions (3.82) was rated slightly lower but still indicated a moderate to high contribution to police misconduct, implying that financial constraints and job dissatisfaction may drive officers towards unethical behavior.

Table 3: Impact of Human Rights Violations on Public Trust in Law Enforcement and Community-Police Relations

Statement	Strongly Disagree n(%)	Disagree n(%)	Neutral n(%)	Agree n(%)	Strongly Agree n(%)	Mean Score	Interpretation
Human rights violations reduce public trust in the police.	23 (2.0%)	56 (5.0%)	112 (10.0%)	401 (36.0%)	523 (47.0%)	4.21	High Impact
Victims of police abuse are less likely to report crimes.	34 (3.0%)	78 (7.0%)	134 (12.0%)	389 (35.0%)	480 (43.0%)	4.08	High Impact
Fear of police misconduct discourages community cooperation.	45 (4.0%)	89 (8.0%)	145 (13.0%)	367 (33.0%)	469 (42.0%)	4.01	High Impact
Frequent violations create hostility between	56 (5.0%)	78 (7.0%)	134 (12.0%)	389 (35.0%)	458 (41.0%)	4	High Impact

citizens and law enforcement.							
Police brutality increases public perception of law enforcement as corrupt.	34 (3.0%)	67 (6.0%)	111 (10.0%)	390 (35.0%)	513 (46.0%)	4.15	High Impact
Human rights abuses erode legitimacy of law enforcement.	45 (4.0%)	101 (9.0%)	167 (15.0%)	378 (34.0%)	424 (38.0%)	3.93	High Impact
Community-police relations improve when officers uphold human rights.	56 (5.0%)	78 (7.0%)	145 (13.0%)	389 (35.0%)	447 (40.0%)	3.98	High Impact

Table 3 highlights the impact of human rights violations on public trust in law enforcement and community-police relations. The findings reveal that human rights violations significantly diminish public trust in the police (Mean = 4.21), with 83% of respondents (Agree + Strongly Agree) acknowledging this impact. Police brutality and corruption (4.15) were also cited as major concerns that worsen public perception of law enforcement. Additionally, victims of police abuse being less likely to report crimes (4.08) indicates that violations discourage public cooperation, which in turn affects crime prevention efforts. The results also suggest that fear of misconduct (4.01) and hostility towards law enforcement (4.00) are prevalent issues, demonstrating how human rights violations foster a negative relationship between the community and the police. However, respondents agreed that restoring accountability (4.07) and upholding human rights (3.98) could rebuild public confidence in law enforcement. This underscores the need for institutional reforms to improve transparency, accountability, and community engagement in policing.

Table 4: Effectiveness of Legal and Institutional Mechanisms in Preventing and Addressing Human Rights Abuses within the Nigerian Police

Statement	Strongly Disagree n(%)	Disagree n(%)	Neutral n(%)	Agree n(%)	Strongly Agree n(%)	Mean Score	Interpretation
The Nigerian legal framework is sufficient to prevent police abuses.	112 (10.0%)	178 (16.0%)	223 (20.0%)	356 (32.0%)	246 (22.0%)	3.40	Moderate Effectiveness

Human rights laws are adequately enforced against police misconduct.	145 (13.0%)	201 (18.0%)	234 (21.0%)	312 (28.0%)	223 (20.0%)	3.24	Low to Moderate
Institutions like NHRC effectively address police violations.	156 (14.0%)	223 (20.0%)	245 (22.0%)	301 (27.0%)	190 (17.0%)	3.13	Low to Moderate
The judiciary ensures accountability for police misconduct.	178 (16.0%)	212 (19.0%)	267 (24.0%)	290 (26.0%)	168 (15.0%)	3.05	Low Effectiveness
The oversight mechanisms (e.g., Police Complaints Response Unit) function properly.	190 (17.0%)	234 (21.0%)	256 (23.0%)	278 (25.0%)	157 (14.0%)	2.98	Low Effectiveness
Citizens have access to justice when police violate their rights.	167 (15.0%)	212 (19.0%)	278 (25.0%)	290 (26.0%)	168 (15.0%)	3.07	Low Effectiveness
Legal reforms have significantly reduced police abuses.	178 (16.0%)	223 (20.0%)	256 (23.0%)	278 (25.0%)	180 (16.0%)	3.05	Low Effectiveness
Strengthening institutional capacity can improve enforcement.	45 (4.0%)	89 (8.0%)	190 (17.0%)	401 (36.0%)	390 (35.0%)	3.90	High Potential for Effectiveness

Table 4 presents the effectiveness of legal and institutional mechanisms in preventing and addressing human rights abuses within the Nigerian police. The findings indicate that the Nigerian legal framework is moderately effective in preventing police abuses (Mean = 3.40). However, human rights laws, institutional oversight, judicial accountability, and access to justice show low to moderate effectiveness, with mean scores ranging from 2.98 to 3.24. Legal reforms have not significantly reduced abuses (Mean = 3.05). However, strengthening institutional capacity has high potential for improving enforcement (Mean = 3.90).

Discussion of Findings

Otodo, Otigbuo, Bako, and Aaron (2024) critically examined the Nigerian government's response to police brutality post-EndSARS, revealing that while reforms were introduced, they failed to enhance transparency and accountability. This aligns with Imegi (2023), who documented various forms of police misconduct, including torture, bribery, and extrajudicial killings. Similarly, Bello and Mela (2022) highlighted unlawful killings and suppression of protests, reinforcing Amnesty International's (2021) findings that police violence in Nigeria persists due to systemic impunity. Further studies, such as Obi and Uzodinma (2024), link human rights violations to Nigeria's declining international reputation, attributing them to weak legal frameworks and political interference. Nwafor (2020) found that despite the National Action Plan on human rights, poor enforcement allows continued abuses. These trends mirror global patterns, as seen in Reiner's (2018) U.S. study, which identified weak accountability as a key driver of police misconduct.

Public trust in law enforcement remains eroded, as Ajanwachukwu, Amah, and Nomeh (2024) noted, with victims discouraged from reporting abuses. Ene (2020) found unchecked police authority in Yenagoa led to widespread human rights violations, while Skolnick (2020) observed similar consequences in Latin America. Institutional responses to police misconduct remain ineffective, as highlighted by Oluka, Ativie, and Agbefe (2021), who noted security forces' unchecked abuses during COVID-19 policy enforcement. Overall, studies consistently indicate that police brutality persists due to corruption, weak oversight, and ineffective reforms.

Conclusion and Recommendations

It is concluded that police brutality in Nigeria persists due to systemic corruption, weak accountability, and ineffective reforms, undermining public trust and human rights protections. Based on the above, it is recommended that the government should strengthen legal frameworks, ensure strict enforcement of police reforms, and establish independent oversight bodies to enhance accountability. Similarly, individuals should actively report misconduct, demand justice through legal avenues, and engage in civic advocacy to push for police accountability. Law enforcement agencies should prioritize human rights training, enforce disciplinary measures against erring officers, and foster community trust through transparent policing practices.

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